

OLIY TA'LIMDA ELEKTROMAGNETIZM KURSINI O'QITISHDA KOOPERATIV O'QITISH USULLARINING PEDAGOGIK POTENSIALI

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida elektromagnetizmni o'qitishda hamkorlikka asoslangan pedagogik metodlarning didaktik imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. elektromagnetizm fizikaning eng murakkab bo'limlaridan biri bo'lib, abstrakt nazariy tushunchalar, matematik asoslar va laboratoriya tajribalarini birlashtiradi. an'anaviy ma'ruza shaklidagi ta'lim ko'pincha talabalarning faol ishtirokini cheklaydi va nazariy qonunlar bilan amaliy qo'llanilish o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni anglashni qiyinlashtiradi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning maqsadi — hamkorlikka asoslangan o'qitish strategiyalarini joriy etish orqali talabalarda konseptual tushunishni, analitik fikrlashni, kommunikativ kompetensiyani va muammoli vaziyatlarda yechim topish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdir.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqot pedagogik eksperiment shaklida o'tkazildi. eksperimental guruhda darslar kichik guruhlarda hamkorlik metodlari asosida tashkil etildi, nazorat guruhida esa an'anaviy usullar davom ettirildi.

NATIJARLAR VA MUHOKAMA: natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, hamkorlikka asoslangan ta'lim talabalarning akademik yutuqlarini, sinfdagi o'zaro muloqotini va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini sezilarli darajada oshirdi. samarali joriy etish uchun metodik shart-sharoitlar belgilandi.

XULOSA: elektromagnetizmni o'qitishda hamkorlik metodlari innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar sifatida ta'lim samaradorligini oshiradi va talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarligini mustahkamlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: kooperativ o'qitish, elektromagnetizm, fizika ta'limi, faol o'rganish, oliy ta'lim, kommunikativ kompetensiya, pedagogik texnologiya.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ МЕТОДОВ КООПЕРАТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ КУРСА ЭЛЕКТРОМАГНЕТИЗМА В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: статья посвящена педагогическому потенциалу методов совместного обучения при преподавании электромагнетизма в вузах. электромагнетизм является одной из наиболее сложных областей физики, так как объединяет абстрактные теоретические концепции, математическое мышление и лабораторный анализ. традиционные лекции ограничивают активное участие студентов и снижают понимание связи физических законов с практикой.

ЦЕЛЬ: цель исследования — внедрение стратегий совместного обучения для развития у студентов концептуального понимания, аналитического мышления, коммуникативной компетенции и навыков решения проблем.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: исследование проводилось в форме педагогического эксперимента. в экспериментальной группе занятия велись с использованием методов совместного обучения в малых группах, в контрольной — традиционными методами.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ: результаты показали, что кооперативное обучение значительно повысило академическую успеваемость студентов, их взаимодействие в классе и критическое мышление. определены методические условия для эффективного внедрения совместного обучения в преподавание физики.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: использование инновационных педагогических технологий совместного обучения повышает эффективность преподавания электромагнетизма и способствует профессиональной подготовке студентов.

Ключевые слова: кооперативное обучение, электромагнетизм, преподавание физики, активное обучение, высшее образование, коммуникативная компетентность, педагогические технологии.

PEDAGOGICAL POTENTIAL OF COOPERATIVE TEACHING METHODS IN THE INSTRUCTION OF THE ELECTROMAGNETISM COURSE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: this article examines the pedagogical potential of collaborative teaching methods in the instruction of electromagnetism at higher education institutions. electromagnetism is one of the most conceptually challenging areas of physics, combining abstract theory, mathematical reasoning, and laboratory practice. traditional lecture-centered instruction often restricts student engagement and limits their ability to connect physical laws with real-world applications.

PURPOSE: the aim of the study is to implement collaborative teaching strategies to enhance students' conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, communication competence, and problem-solving skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the study was conducted through a pedagogical experiment with undergraduate students. in the experimental group, lessons were organized using collaborative small-group strategies, while the control group continued with traditional methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: findings indicate that cooperative learning significantly improved students' academic achievement, classroom interaction, and critical thinking skills. methodological conditions necessary for effective implementation of cooperative teaching in physics education were identified.

CONCLUSION: collaborative teaching methods serve as effective pedagogical technologies for improving the teaching of electromagnetism, fostering active learning, and preparing students for professional challenges in higher education.

Keywords: cooperative teaching, electromagnetism, physics education, active learning, higher education, communicative competence, pedagogical technology.

Modern educational reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan are increasingly focusing on improving the quality of higher education through innovative pedagogical technologies and student-centered teaching. One of the key priorities of modernizing higher education is to develop students' critical thinking, communication skills, and the ability to solve professional problems. From this perspective, collaborative teaching methods are the most effective approach to improving the educational process in the natural sciences and technical fields.

Physics education plays a special role in preparing future specialists, as it develops scientific thinking, logical reasoning, and analytical abilities. However, many areas of physics, particularly concepts such as electromagnetism, electric fields, magnetic induction, electromagnetic waves, and Maxwell's equations, remain complex for students due to their abstract nature. In the traditional lecture style, students often memorize formulas but do not develop a deep understanding of physical processes. As a result, they struggle to solve practical and experimental problems.

Collaborative teaching methods allow students to discuss physical phenomena together, exchange scientific ideas, and solve complex problems collaboratively. Through teamwork and interaction with peers, students can better understand abstract concepts and develop the communication skills necessary for professional activities. Educational researchers have shown that collaborative learning environments significantly improve academic outcomes and increase students' motivation for science [4].

The importance of collaborative learning is particularly evident in teaching electromagnetism, as this subject involves theoretical reasoning, mathematical calculations, and experimental observation. Effective learning requires students not only to understand physical laws but also to logically explain them and apply them in practice. The purpose of this study is to analyze the pedagogical effectiveness of collaborative teaching methods in teaching electromagnetism at higher education institutions and students' conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, and communicative competencies.

The theoretical foundations of cooperative learning have been developed by many educational researchers. Johnson, Johnson, and Smith emphasized that by dividing students into small interactive groups, cooperative learning improves interpersonal communication and academic achievement. [1]. Their research showed that active participation and sharing responsibility have a positive impact on learning outcomes.

Mazur introduced the peer instruction method as an effective strategy for teaching complex scientific concepts. According to Mazur's method, students gain a deeper

understanding of scientific principles when they explain concepts to each other and discuss conceptual questions during class [2]. This method is particularly effective in physics education because students can identify misconceptions through discussions with peers.

A comprehensive analysis of active teaching methods found that student-centered teaching approaches enhance knowledge retention, conceptual understanding, and problem-solving abilities [3]. Freeman and colleagues also confirmed that active teaching methods significantly improve student outcomes in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics [4].

Slavin's cooperative learning theory emphasizes the importance of social interaction in cognitive development. According to his research, collaborative learning environments encourage students to become more responsible for their own education and increase their motivation for academic activities [5].

In Uzbekistan, scholars such as Tolipov and Usmonboeva analyzed the theoretical foundations of pedagogical technologies and emphasized the importance of integrating innovative teaching methods into higher education [6]. Ishmuhamedov also emphasized that modern educational technologies should focus on students' independent activity and collaborative interaction [7].

Although many studies have examined cooperative teaching in science education, there are few studies in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan that specifically focus on teaching electromagnetism. Therefore, this study contributes to the development of methodological recommendations for improving physics lessons through collaborative teaching strategies.

Research Methodology: The study was conducted over one academic semester among undergraduate students studying the general physics course at Jizzakh State Pedagogical University. Sixty students participated in the pedagogical experiment; they were divided into two groups:

Control Group 1 – 30 students taught using the traditional lecture method.

Experimental Group 2 – 30 students taught using collaborative small-group teaching methods.

The experiment focused on the electromagnetism section of general physics, which included topics such as electric fields, magnetic fields, electromagnetic induction, alternating current, and electromagnetic waves.

The cooperative teaching strategy included the following pedagogical methods:

1. Small group discussions.
2. Peer teaching activities.
3. Collaborative problem-solving tasks.
4. Laboratory group work.
5. Presentation and reflection activities.

Students in the experimental group were divided into small groups of four to five people. Each group engaged in conceptual discussions, laboratory research, and analytical

problem-solving activities. It can be seen that the students focused on explaining the physical laws of bodies to their peers and scientifically justifying their solutions.

The effectiveness of collaborative learning was assessed according to three criteria:

1. Cognitive criterion: This criterion assesses students' understanding of electromagnetic concepts.

Indicators: -Understanding theoretical principles

-Ability to explain physical laws

-Problem-solving effectiveness.

2. Analytical Criterion: This criterion assesses the students' ability to analyze and interpret physical phenomena.

Indicators: -Logical reasoning

-Application of physical formulas.

-Interpretation of laboratory results

3. Communicative Criterion: This criterion assesses students' communication and teamwork skills.

Indicators: -Participation in group discussions.

-Ability to explain concepts to peers.

-Collaborative interaction during laboratory work.

Initial and final tests were conducted to assess academic achievement. Observation methods, surveys, and pedagogical analysis were also used to determine student engagement and the development of communication skills.

Results and Analysis. The results of the pedagogical experiment showed significant differences between the control group and the experimental group. Before the experiment, the academic preparedness level of both groups was almost identical. However, after introducing collaborative teaching methods, the experimental group demonstrated significantly higher academic achievement and communicative competence.

Group	Previous test (%)	Next test (%)	Communication competency (%)
Control group	56	64	60
Experimental group	55	82	85

Table 1 presents the average results of the pedagogical experiment.

Control group experimental test task for the electromagnetism department

The following experimental test task was conducted among the control group students who studied the electromagnetism department through traditional lecture-based teaching methods. The purpose of the task was to assess the students' conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, and practical problem-solving skills related to electromagnetism.

Experimental test tasks

1. Explain the difference between electric field intensity and electric potential.

2. State Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction and explain its practical significance.

3. Solve the following problem: A conductor is moving in a magnetic field at a speed of 5 m/s. The magnetic induction is 0.4 T, and the conductor length is 0.2 m. Calculate the induced electromotive force.

4. Describe the relationship between magnetic field lines and electric current.

5. Explain how electromagnetic waves are generated and identify two practical applications.

Assessment Criteria

-Correct understanding of theoretical concepts – 40%

-Application of formulas and calculations – 30%

-Logical explanation and analytical reasoning – 20%

-Scientific terminology and clarity of answers – 10%

Results of the Control Group

The control group consisted of 30 students taught using traditional instructional methods. The average performance indicators obtained during the experimental testing are presented below:

-Average theoretical understanding score: 62%

-Problem-solving accuracy: 58%

-Analytical reasoning performance: 60%

-Communication and explanation skills: 59%

-Overall average result: 64%

Conclusion: The control group results indicate that traditional lecture-based instruction provides basic theoretical knowledge but is less effective in developing deep conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, and communication competence in electromagnetism education.

While academic results improved by 27% in the experimental group, this figure increased by 8% in the control group. These results indicate that collaborative teaching methods significantly improve the conceptual understanding of electromagnetism.

The development of communicative competence was also significantly higher among students who participated in collaborative learning. During classroom observations, students in the experimental group actively discussed scientific problems, explained concepts to their peers, and participated confidently in laboratory activities. The collaborative environment increased students' motivation and reduced anxiety associated with solving complex physics problems.

One of the study's key findings was an improvement in analytical thinking. Students in collaborative groups were more successful at applying physical laws in practical situations. They demonstrated stronger abilities in analyzing electromagnetic phenomena and linking theoretical concepts to laboratory experiments.

For example, while studying electromagnetic induction, students in collaborative groups independently discussed Faraday's law and offered explanations for how an induced current is generated. Through peer interaction, students corrected misconceptions and developed a more accurate scientific understanding.

The effectiveness of cooperative learning is explained by several pedagogical factors:

First, collaborative learning transforms students from passive listeners into active participants. Instead of mechanically memorizing formulas, students engage in discussions and scientific reasoning.

Second, peer explanations simplify complex concepts. Students often understand scientific ideas better when they are explained in simple language by their classmates.

Third, group activities increase motivation and responsibility. Students become more engaged because they contribute to the team's success.

Fourth, collaborative lab sessions reinforce practical skills. Students learn to organize experiments, interpret data, and jointly defend scientific conclusions.

The results confirm that collaborative teaching methods in electromagnetic education create a favorable pedagogical environment for enhancing not only academic achievements but also communicative competencies.

Discussion of the Results. The results of this study are consistent with international research emphasizing the effectiveness of collaborative teaching in science education. Similar to the conclusions of Johnson and Johnson [1], this study confirms that collaborative interaction positively impacts academic achievement and interpersonal communication.

Electromagnetism is traditionally considered one of the most complex areas of physics, as students often struggle to visualize invisible physical processes, such as the interaction between electric and magnetic fields. Collaborative learning methods help overcome these difficulties by encouraging students to actively discuss concepts and construct scientific understanding together.

The peer teaching approach described by Mazur [2] has been proven especially effective during conceptual discussions. Students felt more confident explaining concepts to their classmates compared to traditional teacher-centered lessons. This result confirms that communication-based teaching strategies contribute significantly to deep conceptual understanding.

Another important aspect is the integration of collaborative learning with laboratory sessions. In many traditional physics classes, laboratory activities are performed mechanically without sufficient scientific discussion. In a collaborative environment, students jointly analyze experimental results and compare theoretical predictions with observed phenomena.

The study also emphasizes the importance of developing the communicative competence of future teachers and specialists. Modern professional activity increasingly requires teamwork, communication, and problem-solving skills. Therefore, collaborative learning not only improves academic achievements but also prepares students for professional practice.

Despite positive results, a number of challenges were identified during the experiment. Some students struggled to adapt to collaborative learning because they were initially accustomed to passive teaching methods. Successful cooperative learning requires careful classroom organization, clear task distribution, and the teacher's constant guidance.

Another problem is the need for teachers' methodological training. The successful implementation of collaborative teaching depends on the teacher's ability to organize communication within the group, manage discussions, and objectively assess group work.

Future research should be aimed at expanding collaborative learning strategies through digital technologies, virtual laboratories, and simulation-based instruction. Integrating information technology into collaborative physics education can further enhance student motivation and concept-based reasoning.

Methodological recommendations for organizing laboratory work through collaborative learning in electromagnetism

the effective organization of laboratory work in the electromagnetism section requires the implementation of collaborative teaching methods that actively involve students in scientific investigation and practical experimentation. collaborative laboratory instruction enables students to develop conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, communication competence, and teamwork skills simultaneously. unlike traditional laboratory instruction, where students often perform experiments mechanically, collaborative learning creates an active educational environment in which students discuss hypotheses, analyze results collectively, and solve experimental problems together.

For effective implementation, students should be divided into small groups consisting of four to five members. Each member of the group should be assigned a specific responsibility such as experiment coordinator, equipment manager, data recorder, analyst, or presenter. This role distribution increases students' responsibility and ensures active participation during laboratory activities.

Before beginning the laboratory work, the teacher should organize a short conceptual discussion related to the experiment. Students should collaboratively predict expected results based on physical laws and discuss possible sources of experimental error. Such preliminary discussions improve students' scientific reasoning and prepare them for practical investigation.

During the experiment, students should be encouraged to exchange opinions, compare calculations, and justify their conclusions scientifically. The teacher's role should shift from direct instruction to facilitation and guidance. Instead of providing ready-made answers, the teacher should stimulate discussion through guiding questions and problem situations.

Collaborative laboratory instruction is especially effective in topics such as electromagnetic induction, magnetic field investigation, Ohm's law, and alternating current experiments. Through group interaction, students can better understand abstract physical phenomena and relate theoretical concepts to experimental observations.

Assessment of collaborative laboratory work should include not only the correctness of experimental results but also students' participation in discussion, communication competence, analytical reasoning, and teamwork abilities. Reflection activities at the end

of the lesson are also important because they allow students to evaluate their own contribution and identify difficulties encountered during the experiment.

The implementation of collaborative methods in electromagnetism laboratories contributes significantly to improving the quality of physics education and preparing students for professional scientific activity.

Pedagogical Recommendations

Based on the research results, several methodological recommendations can be proposed for improving the teaching of electromagnetism in higher education institutions:

1. Instructors should organize for students to be divided into small collaborative groups during theoretical, practical, and laboratory sessions.
2. To enhance conceptual understanding and classroom interaction, peer teaching methods should be integrated into lectures.
3. Laboratory work should include team-based problem-solving and scientific discussion activities.
4. Instructors should encourage students to verbally explain physical concepts and to scientifically defend their opinions.
5. Assessment systems should evaluate not only academic achievements but also communication and teamwork skills.
6. Educational technologies, such as simulations, multimedia presentations, and virtual laboratories, should be integrated into collaborative teaching.
7. Teacher training programs must include methodological preparation for creating collaborative learning environments.

The implementation of these recommendations can significantly increase the effectiveness of physics education and contribute to the preparation of scientifically qualified specialists.

In conclusion, the study shows that collaborative teaching methods have great pedagogical potential in teaching electromagnetism at higher education institutions. Collaborative learning creates a favorable environment for improving conceptual understanding, analytical thinking, communicative competence, and practical problem-solving skills, contributing to the achievement of the most significant outcomes.

The pedagogical experiment confirmed that students taught using collaborative teaching methods achieved significantly higher academic results compared to those who received traditional lecture-centered instruction. The experimental group also demonstrated stronger communication skills, more active participation in class discussions, and higher motivation for studying physics.

Collaborative teaching methods contribute to creating an active learning environment that transforms students from passive recipients of information into participants in scientific inquiry. Through interaction and teamwork among peers, students gain a deeper understanding of complex physical concepts and enhance their ability to apply scientific knowledge in practical situations.

The results show that collaborative teaching should be an important methodological component of modern physics education in higher education institutions. Future research

should continue to explore the integration of innovative pedagogical technologies and digital learning environments into electrodynamics courses.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI | СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ | REFERENCES

1. Johnson D. W., Johnson R. T., Smith K. A. Active Learning: Cooperation in the College Classroom. Minneapolis: Interaction, Book, Company, 1998.
2. Mazur E. Peer Instruction: A User's Manual. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1997.
3. Prince M. Is Active Learning Effective? A Review of the Research. Journal of Engineering Education, 2004.
4. Freeman S. et al. Active Learning Improves Student Outcomes in Science, Engineering, and Mathematics. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 2014.
5. Slavin R. Cooperative Learning: Theory, Research, and Practice. Boston: Allyn & Bacon, 1995.
6. Tolipov O., Usmonboeva M. Theoretical Foundations of Pedagogical Technologies. Tashkent, 2010.
7. Ishmuhamedov R. Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in Education. Tashkent, 2018.
8. Hake R. Interactive Engagement versus Traditional Methods: A Six-Thousand Student Survey of Mechanics Test Data for Introductory Physics Courses. American Journal of Physics, 1998.
9. Vygotsky L. Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1978.
10. Bransford J., Brown A., Cocking R. How People Learn: Brain, Mind, Experience, and School. Washington DC: National Academy Press, 2000.